

Closed File Information and Search Service

a program of the
Illinois Department of Children and Family Services

Program delivered by

Midwest Adoption Center
 2860 South River Road – Suite 450
 Des Plaines, Illinois 60018-6008
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 Fax: 847-298-9097
 MAC@macadopt.org
 www.macadopt.org

Service Request Form

To request service, please complete this form and return it to Midwest Adoption Center at the address above. **Please note that your signature must be notarized before we can begin processing your request.**

Contact Information			
My name at this time	First name	Middle initial	Last name
	My address		
Street address			
Apartment, PO Box			
/			
City		State	Zip Code
Phone and e-mail	Work phone number		Home phone number
	Cellular/Other Phone		E-mail address
Personal data	Date of Birth		Social Security Number

Service Being Requested	
I am:	<input type="checkbox"/> An adoptee <input type="checkbox"/> A birth parent <input type="checkbox"/> A birth relative <input type="checkbox"/> An adoptive parent of a minor child <input type="checkbox"/> An adult who was in the care of IDCFS, never adopted <input type="checkbox"/> A guardian <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)
I am requesting:	<input type="checkbox"/> Information or documents from my file. Indicate exactly what you hope to receive:
	<input type="checkbox"/> A search to locate someone:
	Name of the person I want to locate (if known)
	Date of birth or approximate age of the person I want to locate
	Person's relationship to me

